

Proposed Digital Marketing Strategy for Textile Companies (Case Study: PT. Aneka Tekstil Indonesia)

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ABSTRACT: PT. Aneka Tekstil Indonesia commonly called ATENDO is a company engaged in the textile sector. ATENDO has been producing textile products for the past three years or so, but until now there are still many people who do not recognize and do not believe in this company. This company faces the problem of a lack of brand awareness and a sense of trust from the public, resulting in several transactions being canceled by potential customers. In the midst of this digitalization era, people get more information and trust a company digitally through the internet. This study aims to help companies deal with problems related to promotional issues using internal and external company analysis. The results of the analysis show that the company has not carried out a marketing strategy through digital marketing. The author proposes the implementation of a new marketing strategy using new digital marketing techniques by creating a website for the company, then implementing SEO, and creating several social media for the company as a means of information and communication for testimonials from customers, some of these strategies are based on the results of internal, external, and SWOT analysis of the company.

KEYWORDS: Brand Awareness, Digital Marketing, Marketing Strategy, Social Media, Textile Industry.

INTRODUCTION

Textile is a process or activity of making fabrics by knitting or weaving yarn, produced from fibers which then the fabric can be used and patterned according to demand, such as in sewing to the dyeing process to be given color [1]. The textile world in Indonesia has been very much starting from large companies to small companies, starting from weaving, knitting, linen, and others. The textile industry is divided into several sectors including (1). Downstream Sector, it is the industry that requires the most manpower in this industry there are several processes such as sewing, cutting, washing, and finishing. (2). Midstream Sector, this industry processes the manufacture of fabrics from yarn origin through the process of knitting, dyeing colors to printing into finished fabrics. (3). Upstream Sector, this industry is an upstream process that produces fiber into a thread, as a raw material for making fabrics.

The textile industry is one of the largest manufacturing industries in Indonesia and in the world. The economic condition for the textile industry can be said to be quite good compared to several other countries, this is due to Indonesia's cooperation with China for imports. [2] Exporting foreign exchange, creating jobs for people, and fulfilling the needs of the states from Tekstil Industry and Textile Products (TPT) was one of the biggest contributions from the industry to the economy of Indonesia. The effect of the hardwork and innovation of the TPT industry owners, which increased exports provided positive input for Indonesia. This is supported by the government so that TPT owners should continue to innovate to survive and follow the rapidly growing global competition. Most of Indonesia's textile production is concentrated in Java (94%), i.e. Jakarta, Bandung, and Semarang which are the main production hubs and there are also upstream industries making fiber. Most textile products in Java are concentrated in Bandung, there are more than 300 textile companies spread across three regions, namely in Bandung Regency, Bandung City, and City Cimahi [2]. The goal of this research is to find Digital Marketing strategies for PT. Aneka Tekstil Indonesia to increase the company's brand awareness, as well as the action plan, should be implemented with determining from the analysis of the internal and external conditions from PT. Aneka Tekstil Indonesia using related concepts and theory.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The business buying decision-making process is divided into eight stages. Purchasing decisions in B2B tend to be more informed than purchasing decisions in B2C, currently buying decision-making in B2B is important and influential, because it is unlikely that buyers

in B2B business make purchase decisions based on advertising only [3]. The business buying decision-making is separated into eight processes (1) Problem Recognition, this process begins when a person in business experiences a problem or knows his own needs that can be met when obtaining the goods or services. This problem can be influenced by the person's internal or external. (2) Need Description, the next stage once the person realizes the need, then he must describe in detail and carefully what he needs so that the others will find a solution to help him. (3) Product Specification, the next process is product specifications in this process usually in the company there is a special team that analyzes what alternatives will be done with the detailed specifications owned. These specifications are in line with the priorities that have been made before. (4) Supplier Search, the next process where the buyer tries to identify the seller or can be called a vendor, in accordance with the standardization owned by the buyer. Then it will be analyzed which vendors or sellers offer according to what is needed, as well as which ones have a good reputation for service and quality. This process usually involves the use of the internet or social media, to find information such as reviews, and recommendations to the specifications of the vendor. (5) Proposal Solicitation, the next process where when the buyer has found several vendor candidates, they will be contacted for further communication. Usually, vendors provide catalogs or offers of their products. However, if the needs are complicated or expensive, then usually a more detailed purchase order (PO) proposal will be made. (6) Supplier Solicitation, the next process occurs if the buyer has determined or selected one-two vendor, an appointment will be made between the vendor and the buyer for negotiation. The selection of vendors is carried out based on the company's reputation, the feasibility of selling products, to the decision of the buyer team which may later become a win-win solution for both parties and will have a positive impact on future transactions. (7) Order-Routine Specification, the next process is after determining the selected vendor, a transaction occurs to list the technical specifications, the amount needed, and the type of product to the warranty. Furthermore, contracts will be entered into as required to manage transactions. (8) Performance Review, the last process where the buyer provides feedback on the performance of the vendor.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research uses qualitative methods, qualitative methods are the type of method by which research is carried out naturalistically by definition, this method is natural without being affected or without manipulation [4]. This research uses primary data and secondary data as methods to obtain the data needed. Primary data is a type of data obtained based on direct information from the main source of the object under study related to variables for a specific purpose of the research-creation process. For this research primary data to get an explanation of business issues will be collected from interviews with internal stakeholders such as directors also employees [5]. In this study, the author conducted interviews with 6 companies, of which 3 Garment companies and 3 Apparel companies spread around the West Java and Jabodetabek regions. Interviews were conducted to see how they looked and what purchasing decisions they would make for PT. Aneka Tekstil Indonesia. A participant is a person or team that is usually directly related to the search for information for decision-making for purchases, including the Administration team, Marketing team, and Directors.

Table 1. List of Respondents

No.	Type of Industry	Buying Center	Status	Location
1.	Garment Industry	Administration Team	Current Customers	West Java
2.	Garment Industry	Marketing Team	Potential Customers	Jakarta City
3.	Garment Industry	Directors	Current Customers	Jakarta City
4.	Baby Apparel	Directors	Potential Customers	Jakarta City
5.	Sports Apparel	Administration Team	Potential Customers	Jakarta City
6.	Daily Apparel	Marketing Team	Current Customers	West Java

Source: Author, 2023

Table 1. explains the list of companies that is respondent to the data collection, these companies are located in several areas of Jabodetabek and West Java. As well as mentioned before, the buying center of the company for decision-making purchases in the company is still held by one person in one team.

ANALYSIS

The author conducted in-depth interviews with the questionnaire conducted by the Business Making Process Theory and Marketing Mix. Based on the results of these interviews, the following analysis results were obtained:

Table 2. Results of In-depth Interview

No.	Type of Industry	Status	Description
1.	Garment Industry	Current Customers	Don't mind with offline interaction
2.	Garment Industry	Potential Customers	Have the desire to interact and transact through social media
3.	Garment Industry	Current Customers	Have the desire to interact and transact through social media
4.	Baby Apparel	Potential Customers	Want a specific proposal and product description digital and also have the desire to interact with the company through social media.
5.	Sports Apparel	Potential Customers	Want a specific proposal and product description digital and also have the desire to interact with the company through social media.
6.	Daily Apparel	Current Customers	Have the desire to interact and transact through social media

Source: Author, 2023

Table 2. explains about results of Interviewing respondents about the digital existence and transactional that the respondent wants from the company. From the results of the analysis conducted by the author, there are some customer's expectations to have to interact with the company through social media. After doing several analyses, the author made some alternatives to overcome business issues including the SWOT analysis.

Table 3. Results of SWOT Analysis

	Helpful	Harmful
Internal Analysis	Strength <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Selling products at affordable prices Able to adjust their requested order The scale of production in large quantities have experienced experts 	Weakness <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of brand awareness Don't have an proper marketing team Don't have digital channel yet The process administration is still manual
External Analysis	Opportunities <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Promotion through social media can reach more buyers The number of local fashion brands Increasing market demand in association 	Threats <ol style="list-style-type: none"> A competitor who entered social media first Price changes from the supplier Not technology literate

Table 3. explains the SWOT analysis of the company based on interview results, internal analysis, and external analysis. Based on the results of several analyses, the company can carry out several promotional activities to increase brand awareness. The company can implement some marketing strategies based on internal and external analysis, that is Sales Promotion, Paid Media, and Social-

Media. For Sales Promotion; The company can offer cooperation with local brands at lower production prices with certain conditions, companies can approach online and offline to several local fashion brands by providing free samples or other cooperation offers. For Paid Media; the marketing team can start branding the companies and products through digital marketing channels, and companies can use ads as a platform for company and product recognition. For Social-Media; the company can start branding products through social media by making up-to-date content to follow the trend. Then to maximize to gain the trust of the customer, the company can conduct surveys to customers or potential customers about customer satisfaction with the company and about social media suits the company well, to optimize the use of social media, companies can add testimonials on the company's website as a form of interaction with customers.

CONCLUSION

PT. Aneka Tekstil Indonesia is a business-to-business company engaged in the textile industry and has several regular customers. But until now a company called ATENDO still uses conventional marketing methods such as word-of-mouth. Proposed solution from the author based on the company's business issues in terms of promotional strategy where currently the company does not have a digital presence. So the author provides a Proposed Digital Marketing Strategy with several steps such as Build Website Company, Do the SEO Optimization, Make Social Media Platform for Company, Doing the Omni Channel, and Collect Testimonies from Customers.

REFERENCES

1. Rusastra, I Wayan. (2017). *Pengembangan Industri Tekstil Nasional: Kebijakan Inovasi Menuju Peningkatan Daya Saing*. Jakarta: Yayasan Pustaka Obor Indonesia.
2. Kemenperin. (2022, Juli 29). *Siaran Pers*. Retrieved from Pulih dari Pandemi, Utilisasi Industri TPT Naik Jadi 70 Persen: <https://kemenperin.go.id/artikel/23435/Pulih-dari-Pandemi,-Utilisasi-Industri-TPT-Naik-Jadi-70-Persen>
3. Strategis. (2018). Data is obtained from <https://jdih.kemenkeu.go.id/fulltext/2018/9~PMK>.
4. Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2012). *Marketing Management 14th Edition*. New Jersey: Pearson.
5. Sugiyono. (2019). *Statistika untuk Penelitian*. Bandung: CV Alfabeta.
6. Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2017). *Metode Penelitian untuk Bisnis: Pendekatan Pengembangan- Keahlian, Edisi 6, Buku 1*. Jakarta Selatan: Salemba Empat.

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